

CONSIDERATION AND STUDY OF THE PROBLEM OF MIGRATION IN PSYCHOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the author tries to explain the reasons for labor migration of people based on research by scientists. When talking about migration, the need to take into account that there is a living person behind this process is emphasized. The issue of the emergence of a psychological approach to the problems of migration and which aspects of migration are most studied is also briefly touched upon.

РАССМОТРЕНИЕ И ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ МИГРАЦИИ В ПСИХОЛОГИИ

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ABSTRACT

В статье автор пытается объяснить причины трудовой миграции людей на основе исследований ученых. Говоря о миграции, подчеркивается необходимость учитывать, что за этим процессом стоит живой человек. Также кратко затрагивается вопрос возникновения психологического подхода к проблемам миграции, какие аспекты миграции наиболее изучены.

In recent years, the scale of human migration activity, which is growing rapidly in the global space, is of interest not only to politicians, but also to scientists in other fields. The problem of migration attracts researchers from various fields of science - political scientists, demographers, anthropologists, philosophers, sociologists, historians, psychologists, lawyers, who focus on a wide range of the most important aspects of migration.

The rapid pace of changes characteristic of the modern stage of society's development creates new problems in the study of the migration problem. A person who has left his

homeland and changed his place of residence should not only learn another language, customs, traditions and culture, but also, if possible, organize his life in a way that maximizes his opportunities and resources. In this regard, the problem of realizing oneself, one's potential and revealing one's potential comes to the fore. As E.V. Galajinsky [6] noted, the problem of self-realization, which arose many years ago, gained not only relevance over time, but also "emerged as an explanatory principle reflecting the universal basis of the existence of man in the world created by himself" has also acquired a methodological status. From this point of view, it seems that in the new conditions of human life, it is necessary not only to adapt to these conditions, but also to show oneself in them, to realize oneself. Therefore, there is a need to study the psychological laws of this process.

However, despite the fact that modern realities are convenient for discussing the problems of migration related to the study of psychological conditions and the mechanisms of implementation of changing activity, psychological resources that allow a person to fully realize his potential in the conditions of migration, this aspect currently remains outside the boundaries of deep scientific analysis.

Modern psychology is increasingly focusing on the study of the whole person as a subject, as an active changer of his life and existence, who has great potential and can open up new opportunities in solving a set of problems. When it is, it reflects more the modern trends of science. Thanks to the active development of the subjective approach in psychology, new opportunities are opening up in research on the problems of human self-awareness in the context of migration. First of all, they are related to the study of subjective qualities, without which the process of self-realization cannot occur. Relying on the main rules of the household-subject approach provides an opportunity to study the characteristics of the process of self-realization in the conditions of migration by means of studying existential and value-meaningful contexts of human subjectivity.[15]

At the same time, until now there are not enough scientific works that reveal the important features of human subjectivity and provide the features of the process of self-realization in the conditions of migration. This aspect reflects an actual problem, because it helps to define new methods of solving psychological and acmeological problems of human life in the conditions of migration, revealing the system-forming role of the subject in the process of self-realization of a person in these conditions in "building his own development, activity, life and existence." helps to give.

This situation is a series of:

- between the orientation of modern psychology to the study of a whole person capable of variable activity and activity beyond the norm, and the tradition of studying the specific features of adaptation of migrants to a new socio-cultural environment in local psychology;[14]
- between the needs of modern society for people with a high level of self-realization and insufficient study of the psychological determinants of this process;
- between the objectively available possibilities of the psychology of the subject to determine the psychological conditions and mechanisms of the manifestation of changing activity in a person in the conditions of migration and the insufficient scientific basis of this problem;
- causes contradictions between the needs of practice in the application of psychological knowledge to solve the problems of self-realization of migrants and their acceptable inclusion

in the new socio-cultural space of life, and the insufficient study of the manifestation of the subjective potential of migrants in psychology.

Most of the scientists studying the acceleration of the migration flow consider this social phenomenon as a kind of social flow and prefer to estimate its amount so that the state can have a certain effect. It represents migration as a faceless mass of people, a mathematical quantity of supposedly random individuals. However, it should not be forgotten that this "mass" is made up of living people and their fate. If the phenomenon of multifaceted migration is simplified as much as possible, its essence means that a certain person makes a decision to change not only his place of residence and work, but also his destiny, and uses all his efforts to implement this decision. This decision is explained by the desire to live in better conditions compared to the current situation. When the amount of such movements increases significantly, a migration flow is formed. Unfortunately, the human, individual level of such a mass phenomenon is often ignored. Generalized information offered by demographic, economic, and geographic approaches is sufficient to understand important trends. They undoubtedly have an important practical value, because it allows to understand the scale of the phenomenon, to compare it with other social processes, to determine its impact on economic development. However, there are certain limitations. First of all, such approaches do not allow thinking about the causes of migration and the mechanisms of its development in the social environment. Denying the socio-psychological components of migration leads to a misunderstanding of the nature of this phenomenon and the pace of change.[13]

Within the framework of the psychological approach, of course, one "behavioral" direction cannot be distinguished, but all of them (stratification theory of human behavior, concepts of general motivation, adaptive behavior, etc.) guide migrants at all stages of the migration process, and research is increasingly important. to a greater or lesser degree affects the various motivations for migration that are becoming a profession. Thus, the consideration of migration as a method of meeting specific needs of individuals or groups, as a behavioral act, where the main place is allocated to the decision-making mechanism, is further developing. A positive decision on migration is particularly related to the idea of "usefulness of place".

Within the framework of migration research, there are very few scientific works with a direct connection to psychology. Psychology has often been criticized for ignoring the various socio-political and geographical contexts that have some basis [4]. For example, there is almost no field of psychology in which migration in the Eurasian context differs sharply from migration in the rest of the world.

Focusing on migration studies:

- modern psychology, first of all, mental health problems of immigrants,
- secondly, integration, discrimination and xenophobia,
- thirdly, deals with relations in mixed families.

It should not be forgotten that behind the concept of "migration" there is always a living creature with its own history - people. Each migrant is an individual who perceives cultural, social and ethnic factors in his own way. Speaking about the person, A.G. Asmolov said, "What does phenomenology reflect in this field of psychology in the study of the person?" there is no clear answer to the question," he says, and continues his opinion and emphasizes: "in research on personality psychology, human motives, individual biochemical characteristics, social roles,

interests, ideals, abilities, will, experiences, skills, abilities, etc. different appearances like s are intermingled in a strange way" [3].

In this context, the idea of a psychological approach to migration appeared in the 19th century and was reflected in the work of the French politician-economist Jules Duval entitled "History of European, Asian and African emigration in the 19th century" [11]. As the Russian demographer Vladimir Alekseevich Iontsev stated in his article "Classification of the main theoretical approaches in the study of population migration" [7], "within this approach, the psychological direction refers to the various motivations of migration, which are followed by migrants at all stages of the migration process, and the study of which is gaining greater importance. "

B.G.Anan'ev, L.S.Vygotsky, A.N.Leontev, S.L.Rubinsteyn interpret the personality as a "supernatural" and "historical" quality in a person that arises as a result of cultural development [1, 5, 9, 10] . According to L. S. Vygotsky, personality is not innate, but a social concept that emerges as a result of cultural development. Therefore, the person is a social concept [5]. A person as a person is formed by interacting with the world and other people [10]. To study personality, it is important to study in which groups its formation takes place [2]. Because it cannot be denied that a new culture, a lifestyle different from the one he has learned, can lead to mental and somatic health disorders in migrants. A large body of empirical evidence suggests that migration poses a significant threat to psychological well-being [11].

In general, all research on migration can be said to follow three main directions in one way or another:

- 1) reasons for migration or grounds for it;
- 2) impact of migration on migrant status;
- 3) covers the impact of migration on the country from which migrants leave and the country that receives them [12].

In summary, it can be said that migration processes, which historically differed in form, scope, intensity and consequences, have undergone significant changes in their characteristics depending on the migration goals. While at first, after leaving the settled areas, pastoral tribes set themselves the goal of acquiring new fertile lands and developing cattle breeding, now the economic aspect, in particular, the goal of providing material well-being to the family of labor migrants, and changing their lifestyle prevails. This is exactly the issue, the reasons for the migration of labor migrants, their relationship with family members left in their country, that is, how they accept the fact that their relatives live in other countries in the hope of earning money, and the psychological impact of this on them. requires.

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